

Contributions of the German DDC Partner to IPCC TG-Data (07/2024-12/2025)

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The aims of the work in 2025 were finalizing AR6-related work and supporting the implementation of TG-Data’s recommendations for AR7 (IPCC, 2023). The general long-term contribution of the DDC at DKRZ to the IPCC is summarized in Stockhause and Lautenschlager (2022). DKRZ has decided not to support the IPCC in AR7 in January 2025 and waived their IPCC Fund share for 2025-2026 negotiated among the DDC Partners, which was designated to support the TG-Data subgroup “Provenance / Complex Citation” work.

DKRZ’s withdrawal from the DDC generated the two challenges:

1. to transition DKRZ’s CMIP input data preservation tasks to a new German DDC Partner by end of 2025, and
2. to find alternative (funding) opportunities for the activity of the TG-Data subgroup “Provenance / Complex Citation” chaired by M. Stockhause (see section 2.2.2).

Due to the deviating time of the LoA in relation to the LoAs of the other DDC Partners, DKRZ lacked funding for joint DDC activities in 07/2024 - 12/2024. Those are included in this report.

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1. Finalizing AR6-related work

Two tasks were carried out to finalize DKRZ's AR6 contribution:

- 1.1 provision of regional data subsets, and
- 1.2 publication of provenance records for figures.

1.1 Provision of Regional Data subsets

The DDC at DKRZ has provided regional data subsets for 12 core variables of their high-volume data of the WCRP Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) since AR4 to support users located in developing and economy-in-transition countries in data download. The additional service of mailing storage devices has been given up due to reduced demand (see Stockhause, 2025) and been replaced by a fine-granular data access option for the AR6 input data from CMIP6.

The steps undertaken were:

- 1) Select datasets according to transparent criteria:
Data from models providing >5 of the 12 variables were included in their latest versions in case of multiple available versions. Data from IITM-ESM could not be included because the Julian calendar used is not supported by the [Climate Data Operators](#) (cdo) package, with which the regional files were created. Datasets from 5 CMIP6 experiments and 34 models were included.
- 2) Download and process files (merge files into a time series and cut regions):
In total 540 regional datasets were archived, organized in 117 data collections.
- 3) Create metadata and a user documentation
- 4) Archive data including quality checks for consistency and completeness
- 5) Register DOIs for the data collections and include them in the DDC catalog and on the dedicated WGI GitHub page:
117 DOIs for the data collections were registered and included in the DDC catalog and the WGI GitHub page (Figure 1)

The data, the applied software and a user documentation of the regional data for AR6 are available online:

- Regional Data (Figure 1): [https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/DDC-AR6-CMIP6-Data-Archival/tree/main/Archived Data#selected-variables-for-regions](https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/DDC-AR6-CMIP6-Data-Archival/tree/main/Archived%20Data#selected-variables-for-regions)
- Code (Stockhause et al., 2025b): [https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/DDC-AR6-CMIP6-Data-Archival/tree/main/Regional Data](https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/DDC-AR6-CMIP6-Data-Archival/tree/main/Regional%20Data)
- Data Documentation [PDF]: [https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/DDC-AR6-CMIP6-Data-Archival/blob/main/Regional Data/IPCC AR6 RegionData.pdf](https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/DDC-AR6-CMIP6-Data-Archival/blob/main/Regional%20Data/IPCC%20AR6%20RegionData.pdf)

Selected Variables for Regions

Selected variables are provided on regions (further information: [IPCC_AR6_RegionData.pdf](#)):

Region	Longitude	Latitude	Data Collections for Variables
Africa	35°W - 72°E	58°S - 40°N	orog sftgif sftlf huss pr psl rds tas tasmin tasmax uas vas
Asia	26°E - 168°W	3°N - 83°N	orog sftgif sftlf huss pr psl rds tas tasmin tasmax uas vas
North America	170°W - 45°W	5°N - 85°N	orog sftgif sftlf huss pr psl rds tas tasmin tasmax uas vas
South America	120°W - 30°W	58°S - 15°N	orog sftgif sftlf huss pr psl rds tas tasmin tasmax uas vas
Australia	68°E - 115°W	58°S - 8°N	orog sftgif sftlf huss pr psl rds tas tasmin tasmax uas vas
Central Pacific	120°E - 70°W	20°S - 20°N	orog sftgif sftlf huss pr psl rds tas tasmin tasmax uas vas
Europe	60°W - 60°E	30°N - 75°N	orog sftgif sftlf huss pr psl rds tas tasmin tasmax uas vas
North Pole	170°W - 45°W	5°N - 85°N	orog sftgif sftlf huss pr psl rds tas tasmin tasmax uas vas
South Pole	120°W - 30°W	58°S - 15°N	orog sftgif sftlf huss pr psl rds tas tasmin tasmax uas vas

Figure 1: [Regional data table](#) in WGI GitHub repo, providing direct access to the datasets

1.2 Publishing provenance information for AR6 figures/Complex Citation pilot

The publication of provenance information for figures based on CMIP6 input data as a pilot implementation of the Complex Citation recommendations of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) [Complex Citation Working Group](#) (Agarwal et al., 2025) connect input data usage information with the figures of the AR7 WGI, codes applied for figure generation, and final datasets generated. The IPCC use case (Stockhouse, 2023) of using the Complex Citation approach for the traceability of the figure generation and for the attribution (credit) to the input data providers such as CMIP6 was one of three basic use cases for the WG, which drove the development of the Complex Citation concept. The experience from the IPCC AR6 pilot implementation has provided useful insights for the implementation of the Complex Citation approach into AR7 aiming at enhancing the traceability of AR7 results. In addition, the Complex Citation pilot enabled the DDC Partner CEDA to attribute CMIP6 data providers according to the CMIP6 data license requirements and contributed

useful information on gaps and requirements for the [RDA Complex Citation Implementation Interest Group](#).

The approach used the IPCC DDC infrastructure at DKRZ to gather information on figures based on CMIP6 input data hosted at DKRZ in the AR6 Reference Data Archive. This was a tedious process because the usage information was not machine-accessible. The concrete steps of the work included:

- 1) Add references to metadata on dataset and collection levels:
This was based on the information available on the figure webpages and in tables in the WGI GitHub repo: [code references](#) and [final datasets](#).
 - a. The final dataset information turned out to be partly inconsistent with a [Google spreadsheet](#), which CEDA used for the coordination of its archival process, esp. several catalog urls could be replaced by DOIs introducing the significant manual effort to access every catalog url to find the corresponding DOI. CEDA catalog entries include data stored in Zenodo. Those catalog links were replaced by the original Zenodo DOIs. DOIs for code and final data were used to gather citation information using the DataCite API. For further identified inconsistencies, the information was manually verified.
 - b. Most of the figure generating codes were archived in Zenodo with a DOI. These were extracted in a semi-automated process from the individual GitHub repos.
 - c. The references to WGI figure pages were automatically generated, verified and altered where deviating from the general construction rule or where missing. They were also used to add missing code references.
 - d. AR6 WGI chapter references and usage in figures were added based on the information provided by [WGI TSU on CMIP6 data usage](#).

Based on available final datasets for figures using CMIP6 datasets, 107 figures could be identified. For 99 of these figures code was provided. In total 40 350 references were added to the metadata of CMIP6 datasets as provenance information for the figure generation and in support of the Complex Citation pilot.

- 2) Discuss and agree with CEDA on structure and content of the provided information:
It was decided to use Zenodo records for the publication of the information on figure generation / provenance. The information is provided in machine-accessible and user-friendly formats as uploaded files: JSON-LD using the [schema.org standard](#) and csv. The JSON-LD uses an extended DataCite metadata format using DataCite recommendations (Stathis et al., 2022) and adding information on the referenced data and code types and structures:

- a. Credit (input dataset collection to be cited/to which credit is to be assigned),
- b. Provenance (dataset contributing information to the generation of the DataProduct),
- c. archivedAt (dataset collection with long-term preservation),
- d. DigitalDocument (referenced papers containing further information),
- e. DataProduct (generated final dataset),
- f. ImageObject (visualization of the DataProduct),
- g. SoftwareSourceCode (software applied to generate the DataProduct),
- h. Chapter (IPCC AR6 WGI chapter in which the DataProduct is used/referenced).

This information is essential for Knowledge Graphs and Indexers to interpret the provenance information, correctly.

- 3) Set-up extraction of metadata in agreed formats:
As the metadata schema is designed to provide information for the stored data (i.e. is centered around metadata entries for CMIP6 data collections and datasets) but not for the referenced figures, the extraction was challenging.
- 4) Set-up record publication process using the Zenodo API
- 5) Publish samples in the Zenodo Sandbox test instance and review with CEDA and the members of the RDA Complex Citation Working Group
- 6) Adjust content based on the review comments and publish the Zenodo records:
In total 107 figures based on CMIP6 data were published with all provenance information through Zenodo (see example Figure 2).
- 7) Add Zenodo record citation entries and references to CMIP6 input datasets in the DDC archive and in the IPCC WGI github repository
- 8) Provide the list of Zenodo DOIs for the 107 figure provenance / Complex Citation records to CEDA
- 9) Provide experience and metadata schema for discussion to the RDA Complex Citation WG and RDA Complex Citation Implementation IG.

The provenance records for the 107 figures of WGI AR6 are available in Zenodo and the applied code is published in the WGI GitHub repo:

- Figure provenance records in Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/ipcc-ar6/records?q=%22CMIP6%20input%20data%20usage%20information%20for%20IPCC%20WGI%20AR6%20figure%22>

- Code shared (Stockhause et al., 2025b):
[https://github.com/IPCC-WGI/DDC-AR6-CMIP6-Data-Archival/tree/main/Provenance Publication](https://github.com/IPCC-WGI/DDC-AR6-CMIP6-Data-Archival/tree/main/Provenance%20Publication)

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Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC-AR6)

Published March 6, 2025 | Version 20250306 Dataset Open Edit New version Share

CMIP6 input data usage information for IPCC WGI AR6 figure 9.7

IPCC Data Distribution Centre

Contributors

Contact person: Stockhause, Martina Editor: Stockhause, Martina

The record contains information on input dataset usage and citation information from the WCRP Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) for the generation of figure 9.7 of the Sixth Assessment Report of Working Group I of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC AR6 WGI). CMIP6 data that were used as input to this figure follow the Data Reference Syntax. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for data identification (provenance) are available for individual datasets as Handle IDs. DOIs for data citation are available on the following dataset collections: CMIP6 DOIs contain all datasets provided by an Earth System model to a CMIP6 experiment. The data subsets of CMIP6 dataset collections used in the IPCC AR6 WGI have DOIs at this granularity of a model contribution to an experiment. The AR6 subset DOIs are included because they reside in a long-term preservation archive hosted by the IPCC Data Distribution Centre (DDC).

The uploaded human-readable csv file provides a list of datasets/Handle IDs used for the generation of this figure grouped by the corresponding dataset collections they belong to. The machine-actionable json-ld file describes the record as Complex Citation Object (see Agarwal et al., 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14106602>) in a preliminary standard, using the following vocabulary to specify the different functions of the contained Linked Digital Objects: Credit (input dataset collection to be cited/to which credit is to be assigned), Provenance (dataset contributing information to the generation of the DataProduct), archivedAt (dataset collection with long-term preservation), DigitalDocument (referenced papers containing further information), DataProduct (generated final dataset), ImageObject (visualization of the DataProduct), SoftwareSourceCode (software applied to generate the DataProduct), Chapter (IPCC AR6 WGI chapter in which the DataProduct is used/referenced).

Use and cite this record when referring to the generation of IPCC WGI AR6 figure 9.7.

Files

fig_9_7.json

```
{
  "@context": "http://schema.org",
  "@id": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14986542",
  "@type": "https://schema.org/Dataset",
  "identifier": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14986542",
  "name": "CMIP6 input data usage information for IPCC WGI AR6 figure 9.7",
  "additionalType": "ComplexCitationObject",
  "author": "I"
}
```

Versions

Version	Date
Version 20250306	Mar 6, 2025
10.5281/zenodo.14986542	

Cite all versions? You can cite all versions by using the DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14986541. This DOI represents all versions, and will always resolve to the latest one. [Read more.](#)

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Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC-AR6)

Figure 2: Provenance record / Complex Citation object pilot published in Zenodo for Figure 9.7

The lessons learned from this implementation of provenance information as Complex Citation pilot provided core information for shaping AR7 described in section 2):

- 1) The work on accessing and comparing the different resources for information on data and code was contributed to the gap and inconsistency analysis (see section 2.1).
- 2) The experience of the gathering of information from multiple inconsistent and not machine-accessible resources was contributed to the formulation of TG-Data's recommendations for AR7 and the provenance/Complex Citation approach implementation in AR7 supporting IPCC Authors, TSU and DDC Partners by centrally gathering of information on data and code in a machine-accessible and standardized form (see section 2.2).

2. Support for IPCC AR7

An analysis of available data for AR6 was coordinated within TG-Data (co-led by David Huard and Martina Stockhause), which contributed to the gap analysis and deriving a vision for Open Science and FAIR data implementation in AR7 as outlined in Stockhause et al. (2024a) and informed the coordination and implementation effort in support of AR7 (section 2.2).

As representative of IPCC TG-Data, the AR7 efforts and requirements are aligned with the external groups

1. [WGCM Infrastructure Panel \(WIP\)](#) of WCRP CMIP: As TG-Data / DDC Stakeholder, the alignment of AR7's requirements with the CMIP7 standards and infrastructure plans is ensured,
2. [Research Data Alliance Complex Citation Implementation Interest Group \(RDA CCI IG\)](#): As Co-lead, the IPCC use case and the IPCC timeline has been contributed to the implementation efforts, and
3. [CODATA Cross Domain Interoperability Framework \(CDIF\)](#): As Member of CDIF, best practices for cross-domain metadata are communicated back to TG-Data
4. [World Data System \(WDS\)](#): The discussion on shared values and collaboration options at the International Data Week 2025 (see section 3.2) resulted in the initiation of a consultation to formalize this collaboration, e.g. as an Associate Member of WDS, which was followed up including the TG-Data Co-Chairs.

2.1 Analysis and report of the AR6 data curation status and gaps

The gap analysis included final data availability in AR6 and an analysis of model data usage in AR6 WGI.

2.1.1 Final data availability in AR6

The analysis of final data availability in the [joint DDC catalog](#) and the AR6 is based on the IPCC AR6 figure pages. For WGI, additionally, the information provided in the [WGI GitHub pages](#) was utilized. The effort was coordinated and documented at: <https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1vyQ3CJUVAFitEHEcNUL5w8OuvsrHlaoy>

Figure 3: AR6 Figure classification summary

The summary of the figure classification, conceptual vs data figures shows that the majority of figures is based on data (Figure 3).

The results of the independent figure classifications of David Huard and Martina Stockhause were reviewed and finally decided by a small TG-Data subgroup. The result was visualized and integrated into the high-level paper on the IPCC Open Science and FAIR data approach (Figure 4). Together with TG-Data's Recommendations (IPCC, 2023) and the reviews and suggestions for improvements were discussed to formulate the vision for a consolidated IPCC Open Science and FAIR data approach for AR7 (Stockhause et al., 2024a).

Figure 4: Final dataset availability in AR6 (source: Stockhouse et al., 2024a; created by David Huard)

2.1.2 Analysis of model data figures in AR6 WGI

The additional analysis of AR6 WGI data usage was based on the information provided by WGI TSU (see [https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/DDC-AR6-CMIP6-Data-Archival/tree/main/Metadata Conformance/input 20220125](https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/DDC-AR6-CMIP6-Data-Archival/tree/main/Metadata%20Conformance/input%2020220125)), which includes only model input data information from 9 chapters (out of 17 components including SPM, TS and Annexes). Therefore, the analysis of input data usage in AR6 WGI is incomplete but provides information on scale and complexity of input data processing for figure generation (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Share of model data figures among data figures of the AR6 WGI; note that only for 9 chapters information on model data usage was provided (chapters 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13/Atlas).

The results of the analysis of the data usage in figures are:

- AR6 WGI includes 514 Figures in 17 Chapters (counting SPM, TS and Annexes as chapters)
- 448 of the 514 figures are classified as Data Figures, i.e. figures based on data

>162 figures are Model Data Figures, i.e. using modelled data of future climate projections (CMIP5, CMIP6, CORDEX, or MPI-GE). The 9 chapters, which provided detailed input data usage, include 331 figures. 294 are Data Figures and for 162 model data information was provided (Figures of model data usage per chapter are provided in Annex A: Model data usage in AR6 WGI chapters).

The CMIP6 model input data was the most used. Analysis of dataset usage per chapter show large differences in the number of datasets used per figure. The analysis of the data-intense chapters 3 and 9, which provided detailed information on model data usage, show similar numbers:

- Chapter 3: The numbers of CMIP6 datasets per figure are: mean=563, min=6, max=2089
- Chapter 9: The number of CMIP6 datasets per figure are: mean=539, min=8, max=2215

The analysis for all chapters of AR6 WGI is available in the spreadsheets at

<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1ISrjX3Zhtn2kMUgz8LkBekZTAWk1sbT8>

and plotted in Annex A: Model data usage in AR6 WGI chapters.

Reasons for incompleteness of final data and input data usage information include time-pressure, lack of capacity, leaving authors and TSU staff members, unclear (novel) data request, a missing practical approach for the provision of the information.

2.1.3 Lessons learned from AR6

The analysis of data use in AR6 showed that the AR6 is data-intense and the data analysis is rather complex and involves intermediate data products. Some of these intermediate data are valuable data products themselves. Apart from the complexity and the data intensity, experiences from authors, TSU and DDC were gathered to derive requirements for an improved implementation of Open Science and FAIR data practices into AR7.

Enhancing the transparency of the AR7 and scaling up the AR6 approach from part to full data coverage require:

- Automation and streamlining the overall data workflow from authors' generation to report and data archival and better integration of data requests into the overall AR7 workflow
- Definition of and provision of metadata in a standardized and machine-readable format
- Improved Author support in generating these standardized metadata
- For an enhanced transparency of the report information in the supplementary materials needs to become machine-accessible, integrated into the report and the impact/credit systems, and accessible by knowledge graphs

The idea of using standardized provenance records for gathering information from the authors from the TG Data F2F 2023 was further developed into a provenance - Complex Citation concept at TG Data F2F 2024 (see section 2.2.2).

2.2 Development of training materials and support of AR7

The work for AR7 is supported by

- Contribution to training materials and documentations for AR7 (section 2.2.1)
- Chairing the TG-Data Subgroup Provenance / Complex Citation, which implements provenance for gathering information on result/figure generation and the evolving Complex Citation standard to document it in the AR7 in collaboration with the RDA Complex Citation groups, the REF and Jupyter projects (section 2.2.2)

2.2.1 Contributions to training materials and documentations

These activities mostly started within the funding period of the other DDC Partners.

1. Core metadata for data:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1HN8mDIYe3hpnYflHZe60OHciEGP6_Revrek8w-vvHVv

With the analysis of the different metadata schemas used by the different DDC Partners in AR6, the base for the development of the core metadata was provided at the DDC/TSU workshop in Singapore in 10/2024:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1AZmCkqUvR5P3nIG-IkcOm_y90v3UmKRt

This analysis was picked up by WGI TSU to derive a mapping of DataCite terminology to the DDC catalog terminology based on DCAT for internal discussion of required metadata information:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1HN8mDIYe3hpnYflHZe60OHciEGP6_Revrek8w-vvHVv

2. Training Materials:

- <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1A7S3fijJ0FzRzZjySssHj0U-wr9DP3fcSJDjh7LrPmQ>
- <https://github.com/IPCC-AR7/ipcc-author-guidance>

3. Author Handbook:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/18p0bmFUCom24GwTLe8F0Bn6mBHtBIpMFQgDFlcAS7B8>

4. TG-Data Transition Document (Vicuna et al., 2025):

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16753378>

5. Coordination of high-level paper (Stockhouse et al., 2024a):

The vision for AR7 was developed during the writing process, which brought together most of the TG-Data Members and ex-officio Members.

The brief introduction to IPCC's FAIR approach (Stockhouse et al., 2024b) consisting of a One-Pager and a recording has turned out to be a central outreach resource, which has been updated in 2024 to reflect the progress, further revisions are planned.

2.2.2 Lead of TG-Data subgroup on provenance / Complex Citation implementation in AR7

The lessons learned from the analysis of AR6 WGI data usage and the experiences of authors, TSU and DDC Partners resulted in the development of the provenance - Complex Citation approach from the initial idea of using provenance information at [TG-Data F2F 2022](#) to the provenance/Complex Citation approach at [TG-Data F2F 2024](#). The discussions were picked up afterwards to form a TG-Data Subgroup led by M. Stockhouse that works on the Complex Citation implementation and its integration into the AR7.

In parallel, the requirements on data attribution and traceability were discussed in an international cross-domain context, which led to the establishment of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Complex Citation Working Group. The [IPCC use case](#) was one of the guiding use

cases for the formulation of the Complex Citation recommendation (Agarwal et al. 2025). The implementation of the Complex Citation is the topic of the follow-up [RDA Complex Citation Implementation Interest Group \(RDA CCI IG\)](#).

The IPCC AR7 [concept](#) (IPCC TG-Data, 2025) aims to include Complex Citation Object (CCO) references in every figure caption, which provides readers access to the figure generation information and enables IPCC authors to give credit to all input data providers in a compact form.

The concept uses standardized provenance records for gathering traceability information from authors and using the Complex Citation approach to document it in every figure caption. The concept formulation in early 2025 was followed by a series of [meetings](#). The envisioned high-level workflow is shown in Figure 6.

The use of provenance records makes the information machine-accessible for use during the editorial process and for the DDC Partners archiving input data. Together with author tool support, the data workflow requires less manual intervention and becomes scalable to capture all data used and generated in AR7.

Key aspects of the provenance / Complex Citation approach are:

- *Aim*: Increased standardization and automation of the workflow allowing to scale up the traceability and achieve a complete data coverage
- *RDA-led*: standardization and implementation of the Complex Citation approach in collaboration with several stakeholders
- *Author support*: Author support and provenance-enabled community tool frameworks in collaboration with [Rapid Evaluation Framework \(REF\)](#) and [Jupyter](#) projects
- *TSU and DDC Partner support*: standardized provenance records enable the automation of the editorial and input data archival processes
- *Enhanced traceability and attribution*: Implementation of traceability of key AR7 results, esp. report figures, by adding CCO references to figure caption, which provides access to provenance information and enables credit assignment for input data providers.

Figure 6: Envisioned integrated data and code workflow for AR7 (source: Stockhouse et al., 2025a)

The early steps in the first half of 2025 concentrated on the provenance harmonization and the international standardization of the Complex Citation approach:

1. Author support/provenance in the REF subgroup:
ESMValtool has been used by several chapters for the generation of figures and provides provenance records complying to the W3C PROV standard. Based on their experience the REF consortium and the IPCC WGI Interactive Atlas representatives harmonize the provenance profile to derive a provenance template for AR7, which is then to be extended to cover the requirements of the Complex Citation approach.
2. Technical integration/Jupyter subgroup:
Jupyter Notebooks were used by several chapters in AR6 to document their figure generation. At AGU 2024, the contact between RDA Complex Citation group and the Jupyter group was established to discuss a potential implementation in Jupyter. The development of a provenance extension to the Jupyter metadata was agreed, picking up the result of the REF subgroup. The integration into the data/software workflow and training activities is discussed.
3. RDA Complex Citation WG/RDA Complex Citation Implementation IG collaboration:
The Complex Citation concept endorsed by RDA is to be implemented in the RDA Complex Citation Implementation IG established in June 2025. Tasks are the standardization of the

Complex Citation Object incl. its publication and stakeholder engagement for the Complex Citation integration into the scholarly attribution/credit system.

Mid 2025 and in consultation with WGI, the Complex Citation implementation into AR7 (see Figure 7) was broken down in individual tasks with priorities and a [roadmap](#) were developed (see Figure 8).

Figure 7: Vision of a full implementation of the Complex Citation approach into IPCC WGI AR7; contributions from IPCC are blue and from external partners black (source: Stockhouse et al., 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15790512>).

Figure 8: Screenshot of the drafted roadmap for Complex Citation implementation (2025-08-14)

In parallel, a 3-step implementation depending on available resources was developed and related to the individual tasks:

1. **Minimal goal "Enhanced Traceability"**: Standardized provenance records are gathered from the IPCC Authors and documented on the Figure webpages. The approach of the IPCC WGI Atlas for the provenance visualization can be used. The machine-accessible gathering of provenance provides a complete and reliable source for the input data archival for the DDC Partners.
2. **Medium goal "Internal Complex Citation Object Usage"**: The Complex Citation approach is half implemented by the publication of Complex Citation Object (CCO) DOIs for every figure. The Figure webpages should become the DOI landing pages. A CCO DOI provider is selected from the early adopters of the RDA Complex Citation Implementation IG members.
3. **Complete goal "Full Complex Citation Implementation"**: The CCOs for every figure are referenced in figure captions and the Complex Citation approach is supported by the AR7 publisher. This option requires a change of the AR7 publication and an IPCC decision.

This activity lacks capacity; therefore, funding options for this work were investigated. To enable continuous progress of this activity during the unfunded transition period of the German DDC in early 2025, a short-term intermediate grant was searched for in addition.

Main resources of the TG-Data subgroup on provenance/Complex Citation:

- Concept:
IPCC Task Group on Data Support for Climate Change Assessments. (2025). Author tool support for AR7 based on provenance and Complex Citation. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15714121>

- TG-Data subgroup meetings/coordination: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1SMBDWm41-AwU6WCm7QobiD4pWL1Dk8e3_KJ7x56ZcF5U/edit
- Roadmap and tasks: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1sXxxjBs3F0ZH0WWfWNPwLOF7rM7apeAWG1D3ccoiAC4>
- Github repo for technical coordination: <https://github.com/IPCC-AR7/jupyter-ipcc-ext/>
- Provenance/Complex Citation Subgroup members:
 - Active Members: Martina Stockhause (DDC, subgroup chair), Mai Hong (WGI TSU), Alessandro Spinuso (TG-Data until 06/2025), David Huard (TG-Data Co-Chair until 06/2025), Lina Sitz (WGI TSU), Greta Adamo (Early career scientist supporting TG-Data since 06/2025)
 - Interested Members: José Manuel Gutiérrez (DDC), Charlotte Pascoe (DDC), Azra Alikadic (WGII TSU), April Lamb (WGIII TSU)
 - External Members: REF project (Jared Lewis, Bouwe Andela), Jupyter project (Fernando Perez, Kirstie Whitaker), NotebooksNow! project (Brian Sedora), RDA Complex Citation Implementation IG (Shelley Stall, Lesley Wyborn, Justin Buck, James Ayliffe, Graham Parton, Deb Agarwal, Jonathan Blythe)
 - Partly supported by CMIP-IPO (until 10/2025 as part of the REF project)

3. Training workshop and outreach activities

Due to the deviating time of the LoA in relation to the LoAs of the other DDC Partners, DKRZ faced the challenge to take part in joint DDC activities and meetings prior the funding period. They have been included in this section. Activities include IPCC-internal meeting participation, outreach in the climate community, and outreach in the data science community.

3.1 Unfunded TG-Data and outreach activities 07/2024 – 12/2025

3.1.1 Internal TG-Data and DDC activities

1. General contributions to TG-Data

- a) IPCC TG-Data / IPCC DDC Stakeholder in the WIP with reporting on CMIP progress at TG-Data meetings
- b) Contribution to DDC Subgroup
- c) Lead of Provenance/Complex Citation Subgroup (see section 2.2.2); transitioned to Activity A9 of Pillar II (see https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1TknJiAfTiwNs1ZrGQTXVnyHIzpyJB7Uo5jEEWJz1WY/edit?slide=id.g3afee0360fc_10_15#slide=id.g3afee0360fc_10_15)
- d) Contributions to TG-Data's regular reports
- e) Annual update of the metadata in the joint DDC catalog and annual Reports for the DDC at DKRZ, e.g. for 2024:

Stockhouse, M. (2025). IPCC DDC at DKRZ: Annual Report 2024. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609247>

2. DDC – TG-Data Training Material preparation

A workshop with TSU members on preparing Training Materials was co-located with the TG-Data F2F 2025. The results are available here:

- Training material preparation document: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1A7S3fijJ0FzRzZjySssHj0U-wr9DP3fcSJDjh7LrPmQ> ;
- GitHub repo [not yet published]: <https://github.com/IPCC-AR7/ipcc-author-guidance>

In preparation of the workshop, the metadata schemas used in AR6 were summarized and compared. Suggestions for improvements were made:

- Preparation of metadata use in AR6 for metadata standardization discussion: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1AZmCkqUvR5P3nIG-IkcOm_y90v3UmKRt

This work provided input for the formulation of the metadata schema for AR7 final datasets prepared by WGI TSU:

- IPCC Metadata Core Fields: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1HN8mDIYe3hpnYflHZe6OOHciEGP6_Revrek8w-vvHVVs/

3. TG-Data F2F 2024 (Singapore, 21 – 25 October 2024):

(<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1scD5Tc8DRoggR49ZqSB3tKbYGlVURj8KwF8brhqtZXA/>) updates to tasks led by DKRZ were provided:

- a) Lead of discussion on Complex Citation / provenance implementation in AR7 (2024-10-23): <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/15AruKRX1FcQvs6yBhgBP-60q1kLHiND0/>
- b) Report on ongoing activities in CMIP7 Fasttrack as IPCC TG-Data stakeholder in the WGCM Infrastructure Panel: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1gsV2Bi0NeiXDIFDXsGU0uxk0AzvGA_3n

Contributions to TG-Data work and reports were provided:

- TG-Data’s handover document (Vicuna et al., 2025): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16753378>
- TG-Data’s workplan: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1NZu6duVYHCytjsJQAZqLezKatApiLqQX>

4. TG-Data F2F 2025 (Frankfurt, 10 – 13 December 2025):

(https://docs.google.com/document/d/1rwLOUdhoIuweo1-U7-fODDCXRMh3xy3CTy_L-mB8EqM) updates to tasks led by DKRZ were provided:

- a) Stockhouse, M., IPCC TG-Data, WCRP-CMIP International Project Office, RDA Complex Citation Implementation IG. (2025, December 11). Reports on CMIP7 and TG-Data Subgroup provenance Complex Citation at TG-Data F2F 2025. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17893583>
- Report on TG-Data Subgroup provenance / Complex Citation:
<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/15AruKRX1FcQvs6yBhgBP-60q1kLHiND0/>
 - Report on the status of CMIP7 input data archival for IPCC AR7:
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1gsV2Bi0NeiXDiFDXsGU0uxk0AzvGA_3n
 - Report on the collaboration with the World Data System (WDS):
<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/10hRSBYNHLYXjziZbRXf8scyOo3m6oJIc>
- b) Report on CMIP7 Fasttrack as IPCC TG-Data stakeholder in the WGCM Infrastructure Panel (provided by CMIP-IPO)

The new members of TG-Data discussed and evaluated ongoing activities and prioritized them as activities to define the TG-Data workplan for 2026. The TG-Data Subgroup provenance / Complex Citation was reestablished as Pillar II Activity 9. Unfortunately, the lost expertise of former TG-Data members could not be compensated. The group still lacks a metadata expert helping to define a solid provenance metadata schema as interface for the authors. As this definition is already behind schedule and is central for all following steps in the workflow including input data archival and the documentation of provenance, these activities are still at risk. The renewed subgroup will have to decide how to go about it.

Further contributions:

- Contribution as expert to the risk log spreadsheet of the DDC:
<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1xJnYngeTfZsg2VWwompC6Ds23K3XNt3yT>
- A contribution to the DDC workplan due end of 2025 was not possible because of the lacking decision for the new DDC partner in Germany. However, the expert judgement of required resources was shared.
- Joining the workflow mapping activity and partnership pillar with initial action item to approach WCRP CMIP to request a formalization of the TG-Data representation as IPCC TG-Data and DDC stakeholder in the WIP.

3.1.2 Outreach Activities

The work of TG-Data and the DDC was presented at several conferences. In context of the Complex Citation approach, RDA WG/IG sessions were co-chaired.

1. [RDA-23](#) (Costa Rica, 12-14 November 2024; funded by DKRZ):

At RDA-23, a direct contact to Cambridge University Press was established and Complex Citation implementation requirements and efforts at the publisher were discussed.

- Co-convenor of RDA Complex Citation WG session:
<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1M0RvejH7GNfVXepdu5jVg2ZKtMEL2uyk>
- Invited speaker at the joint session "Implementing and Facilitating Data Review in Data Repositories" of the Repository Platforms for Research Data IG and the Domain Repositories IG at RDA-23:
Stockhouse, M. (2024, November 14). Approaches and Challenges of Reviewing Research Data in Climate Science - Focus on CMIP and IPCC -. RDA 23rd Plenary Meeting (RDA23), San José, Costa Rica (Hybrid). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14399742>
- DataCite Connect side-event

2. Virtual [RDA-24](#) (7-11 April 2025; funded by RDA):

Co-convenor of RDA Complex Citation WG session: https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-citations-working-group/plenary-participation/?application_id=174612

3. [REF Hackathon](#) (Exeter, UK, 10-13 March 2025; virtual participation, no fees):

Contribution to several discussions on provenance and introduction of the IPCC AR7 plans on provenance usage and Complex Citation implementation; the collaboration on provenance was agreed

4. [AGU 2024](#) (Washington, USA, 9-13 December 2024; funded by [DE-IPCC](#) (travel expenses) and M. Stockhouse (conference fees)):

At AGU, the contact to the Jupyter project was established and a collaboration on the Complex Citation implementation into AR7 was discussed, leading to the ongoing collaboration (see section 2.2.2).

a. DDC Manager meeting

b. eLightning presentation:

Stockhouse, M., Gutiérrez, J. M., Xing, X. (2024). Benefit and limitations of the application of the TRUST principles on the jointly managed IPCC Data Distribution Centre. AGU24, Washington D.C., USA. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14626703>

c. Poster Co-Author:

- Collaborations across boundaries in the Data Distribution Center (DDC) of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate

Change (IPCC) to support climate assessments and interdisciplinary applications

- Implementing FAIR Data Principles in IPCC AR6 WGI Report
- Using Complex Citations to Close the Provenance Gap Between IPCC AR6 figures and CMIP6 Simulations

d. Session Co-Convener:

- Collaboratively Advancing Trust in Data Repositories and Integrated Infrastructure to Enable Interdisciplinary Research, Applications, and Uses of Open Data
- Enhancing Research and Climate Change Assessments Through Open Data, FAIR Principles, Persistent Identifier Interconnections, and Funder Mandates
- Complex Citations: Ensuring Transparency, Reproducibility, and Credit for All Supporting Research Contributions

5. [EGU 2025](#) (Vienna, Austria, 27 April - 2 May 2025; funded by DKRZ):

During a meeting with another Co-Chair of the finalized RDA Complex Citation WG, the Statement of Work for the RDA Complex Citation Implementation IG (CCI IG) was drafted. This IG is to develop the required standards for the Complex Citation concept and work on its implementation in a stakeholder engagement process. The Statement of Work was submitted in May 2025 and the CCI IG was established by RDA in June 2025.

a. DDC Manager meeting

b. Convener: ESSI3.1 [Collaborations, Tools and Services Towards an Integrated Research Data Infrastructure](#)

c. Presentation:

Stockhause, M., Sitz, L., Pascoe, C., Agarwal, D., Ayliffe, J., Buck, J., Damerow, J., Gutiérrez, J. M., Hassler, B., Hoffman, F. M., Parton, G., Lewis, J., McRae, M., Stall, S., Wyborn, L. (2025). How can the Complex Citation be implemented in the IPCC AR7 using existing frameworks and interactive notebooks?, EGU General Assembly 2025, Vienna, Austria, 27 Apr-2 May 2025, EGU25-15036, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-15036>.

d. Co-Author on presentations

- Xing, X., Delgado Ramos, G. C., Alikadic, A., Lamb, A., Stockhause, M., Sitz, L. E., Milward, A. (2025). Challenges and opportunities in implementing open and FAIR data in Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Seventh Assessment Report (AR7), EGU General Assembly 2025, Vienna, Austria, 27 Apr-2 May 2025, EGU25-19487, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-19487>.
- Ayliffe, J., Agarwal, D., Buck, J., Damerow, J., Parton, G., Stall, S., Stockhause, M., Wyborn, L. (2025). Transparency

in open science outputs -: Ensuring Transparency, Reproducibility, and Credit for All Supporting Research Contributions, EGU General Assembly 2025, Vienna, Austria, 27 Apr-2 May 2025, EGU25-19351, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-19351>.

6. [JpGU 2025](#) (Chiba, Japan, 25 - 30 May 2025; invited talk; virtual participation funded by DKRZ):
Stockhause, M., Sitz, L., Pascoe, C., Huard, D., Pirani, A. (2025, May 26). The Open Science approach of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Japan Geoscience Union Meeting 2025 (JpGU 2025), Chiba, Japan, and online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15363244>
7. [CODATA Workshop "Metadata Models and Services Typologies in Digital Resource-Sharing Frameworks"](#) (invited expert; funded by DKRZ)
The provenance metadata schema of DDI-CDI was discussed with the participants using an example from social sciences. A colleague from the RDA Complex Citation Implementation IG discussed integration options for the Complex Citation metadata into the CODATA Cross Domain Interoperability Framework ([CDIF](#)) supporting EOSC's strategic goals.
8. **AGU 2025** (New Orleans, USA, 15-19 December 2025; no funding for participation in conference and DDC Manager meeting available):
 - Co-author of CIESIN's contribution:
Data Curation through Governance and Stewardship in Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Seventh Assessment Report (AR7)
 - Co-organizer of Complex Citation townhall

3.2 Funded TG-Data and outreach activities 01/2025–12/2025

[IDW 2025](#) / [RDA-25](#) / [SciDataCon 2025](#) (Brisbane, Australia, 13-16 October 2025; funded through DDC travel budget of IPCC Funds):

- RDA Complex Citation Implementation IG:
 - Co-convener of Complex Citation Implementation IG Session: https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-citations-working-group/plenary-participation/?application_id=188000
 - Presentation of RDA Complex Citation WG recommendations in RDA Impact and Adaptation session: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1gwmYh5CjxGgX8vxn1kQcoG60c3Sfj30yb-0VJyfnmgo>
related also to IPCC-AR6 proof of concept of the Complex Citation recommendations: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/adoption-stories/enhancing-the-transparency->

[of-scientific-assessment-results-and-the-attribution-of-credit-for-data-providers/](#)

- RDA CCI IG Poster (RDA-25; <https://www.rda-alliance.org/plenaries/idw-2025/poster-exhibition/>):
"Complex Citation Implementation IG: Let's realize the concept !"
- Poster for IPCC AR7 (SciDataCon 2025; <https://scidatacon.org/event/9/contributions/206/>):
Stockhause, M.; Sitz, L.E.; Alikadic, A.; Lamb, A.; Pascoe, C.; Xing, X. (2025). Plans and challenges for FAIR and open data and an enhanced transparency of the IPCC Seventh Assessment Report. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15790512>
- World Data System (WDS): Discussion on options/opportunities to strengthen the collaboration with TG-Data as we share common values like long-term preservation and sustainability of research outputs. One option is an Associate Membership¹ of IPCC TG-Data. It was agreed to follow up on this.
- Co-located event [CODATA Initiatives WorldFAIR+ and CDIF](#) (12 October 2025):
 - Opportunities and overlaps with the IPCC plans on provenance and Complex Citation were contributed to the discussion together with the need to include data and software citation into the aim for provenance and quality, because credit or attribution for providing input datasets is essential and contributes to the trust and transparency of the result.
 - IPCC was introduced as a use case for provenance because of the unique conditions of IPCC TG-Data and the IPCC AR7 process, which includes the researchers or IPCC authors, who are essential for the required community change in provenance documentation and citation of digital objects. This is to be followed up on in the next CDIF meetings including the upcoming Dagstuhl workshop in November 2025.
- Co-located event ["The Long-term Data Workflow from Creator to Re-user: How Can This Be Managed Best for Future Benefit for Research and Development of Predictive Tools"](#) (17 October 2025):
 - Exchange with other data stewards and data policy experts on best practices for data, our challenges and needs. There was an agreement that the funding model has to change, as traditional funders reduce their engagement and the effort for the global good has to be resourced by more than the current 12% of the world's population.
- Co-located event [DataCite Connect](#) including a casual get-together (17 October 2025):

¹ Associate Members are organizations that are interested in the WDS endeavour and participate in our discussions, but that do not contribute direct funding or other material support (ISC National Members, Academies, and some commercial entities could be in this category) [source: <https://worlddatasystem.org/members/>].

- o The contact with DataCite was renewed after several staff changes at DataCite. It was agreed that the responsible person at DataCite will get in touch and that DataCite will be included in the work of the RDA Complex Citation Implementation IG to establish a close exchange with DataCite.
- o The needs of the IPCC AR7 provenance and Complex Citation plans were raised the ongoing work of the RDA Complex Citation Implementation IG was introduced as current challenge. Other DataCite members agreed on the challenge to cite many datasets. The Complex Citation approach is not limited to the use in scientific publications but can also support downstream data (product) providers.

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Annex A: Model data usage in AR6 WGI chapters

A.1 Citation Granularity (data collection with DOIs)

A.2 Dataset Granularity (relevant for traceability)

